

JISMONIY MASHQLAR ORQALI CHIDAMLILIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA YUKLAMALARNI MEYORLASHTIRISH USHLUBLARI

*Termiz davlat pedagogika instituti
Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlar nazariyasi va
metodikasi*

mutaxassisligi 2-kurs magistranti.

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***Annotatsiya:** Ushbu maqolada jismoniy tarbiya vositalari orqali yoshlarni chidamlilik sifatlarini rivojlantirishning o'ziga xoy yo'llari va yuklamalarning sportchi organizimi uchun taqsimlashga oid asosli ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Jismoniy tarbiya, yuklama, vosita, tabiatning sog'lomlashtiruvchi kuchlari, jismoniy mashqlar, gigiyenik omillar.*

Jismoniy salomatlikni mustahkamlashning samarali vositalaridan biri jismoniy mashqlardan foydalanish xisoblanadi. Umumiy chidamlilikni rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan jismoniy mashqlar (yugurish, suzish, velosipedda yurish, chang'i, konkida uchush va bosh.) bilan shug'ullanish yoki aerob mashqlar organizmda ijobiy o'zgarishlarning sodir bo'lishiga olib keladi. Jismoniy faollikning aynan shu turini ko'pincha mutaxassislar sog'liqni mustahkamlashning asosiy vositasi deb xisoblaydilar. Biroqbugungi kunda shug'ulanuvchilar organizmining funksional imkoniyatlari asosida chidamlilikni rivojlantirishda jismoniy yuklamalar hajmi va shiddatini meyorlashtirishni optimal xolatga keltirish masalasi yetarlicha yoritib berilmagan.

Bularning barchasi chidamlilikni rivojlantirishda jismoniy yuklamalarni individual tarzda meyorlashtirish usuliyatini ishlab chiqish uchun asos bo'ldi. Aerob mashqlarni bajarganda, jismoniy yuklama hajmi deganda mashq bajarish uchun sarflangan vaqt, jismoniy yuklama shiddati deganda esa, vaqt birligi ichida mashq bajarish sur'ati (chastotasi) nazarda tutiladi.

Optimal jismoniy yuklamani aniqlash uchun shug'ullanuvchilarning funksional xolati darajasini aniqlab olish zarur.

Ma'lumki, chidamlilikni rivojlantirishga yunaltirilgan mashqlarni bajarganda, birinchi navbatda, shug'ullanuvchilar organizmidagi yurak-qon tomir va nafas tizimlari faoliyatida o'zgarishlar yuz beradi. (yurak qisqarishlari sur'ati ortadi, arterial qon bosimi ko'tariladi, o'pka ventilyatsiyasi kuchayadi va h.k).

Jismoniy tarbiya amaliyotida yurak-qon tomir tizimi funksional holatini aniqlashning eng keng tarqalgan usullaridan biri Rufye sinovidir (RS). Mazkur sinov yurak-qon tomir tizimining jismoniy yuklamaga javob reaksiyasini aks ettiradi. RS kuyidagicha xisoblanadi.

$RS = (4 (YUQS 1 + YUQS 2 + YUQS 3) - 200) / 10$, Bunda RS –Rufye sinovi, ballar (0-3-a'lo, 3,1-6- yaxshi; 6.1-10-qoniqarli; 10,1-15-qoniqarli,> 15 – yomon); YUQS 1 – tinch xolatda YUQS (5daqiqali dam olishdan so'ng o'tirgan xolatda 15sek. ichida o'lchanadi). YUQS 2 - 45sek. davomida -30 marta o'tirib turgandan keyingi YUQS (15 sek. ichida o'lchanadi); YUQS3 – yuklamadan keyingi bir daqiqilik dam olishdan so'ngi YUQS (15 sek. ichida o'lchanadi).

Ilmiy –uslubiy va pedagogik amaliyot tahlili asosida biz chidamlilikni rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan uch xil eng keng tarqalgan mashqlarni tanlab oldik: yugurish, step-test, joyida turib yugurish.

Jismoniy yuklamalar hajmi va shiddatining optimal kattaliklarini aniqlash uchun aerob siklik mashqlarni bajarish vaqtida izlanishli pedagogik tajriba o'tkazildi. Xar bir talabaga uchala mashqni muayan (maksimal) shiddat bilan bajarish taklif qilindi. Masalan talabalar xar daqiqada 160 yugurish qadami shiddati bilan yuguradilar. Xar ikki daqiqada ularning tomir urishi o'lchanadi. Talabalar charchoqning ilk belgilari paydo bulgunga qadar xarakatni davom ettiradilar.

Keyingi mashg'ulotda talabalar xuddi shu mashqlarni shiddatini 10% ga tushirib bajardilar. Har safar mashq bajarilganidan keyin shiddat 10%ga pasaytirib berildi va bu talabaning tomir urishi mashq bajarilganidan so'ng 120/dan yuqori bo'lmaguncha damom ettirildi. Shu tariqa biz mashq bajarish

shiddati turlicha bo'lganida talabada YUQSnini hamda mashq bajarish uchun uning sarflangan vaqtini aniqlaymiz. Olingan ma'lumotlar shuningdek, talabalarning individual RS ko'rsatkichlari statistik jixatdan tahlil etilib, shundan so'ng shug'ullanuvchilarning RS natijalariga ko'ra jismoniy mashqlarning optimal xajmi xamda shiddati, mashq bajarish paytida erishish kerak bo'lgan YUQSnini bashorat qilish uchun imkon beruvchi ko'plab chiziqli regressiya tenglamalari tuziladi. Talabalarning jismoniy mashqlari optimal shiddatini aniqlash mumkin bo'lgan ko'plab chiziqli regressiya

tenlamalari (modellar) qo'yidagi ko'rinishga ega (1-12 formulalar):

$$1\text{-sonli ma SH (yigitlar)} = 520632 - 2,22692 \times RS + 0,812565 \times YUQS$$

(3) shq. Yugurish (yugurish qadamlari miqdor/ daq.)

$$SH(\text{qizlar}) = 47,1878 - 2,22692 \times RS + 0,812565 \times YUQS \quad (1)$$

$$T(\text{qizlar}) = 153,332 - 1,11391 \times RS - 0,800235 \times SH \quad (2)$$

$$SH(\text{yigitlar}) = 520632 - 2,22692 \times RS + 0,812565 \times YUQS \quad (3)$$

$$T(\text{yigitlar}) = 159,332 - 1,11391 \times RS - 0,79023 \times SH \quad (4)$$

Bunda SH – mashq bajarish shiddati, yugurish qadamlari miqdorlari daq; IR robinson indeksi, ballar; YUQS - mashq bajarish paytidagi yurak qisqarishlari sar'ati;

T – mashq bajarishga sarflangan vaqt.

2- sonli mashq. Step-test (qadamlar miqdorlari/daq.

$$SH(\text{qizlar}) = 54,8957 - 3,45151 \times RS + 1,2594 \times YUQS \quad (5)$$

$$T(\text{qizlar}) = 65,2213 - 1,06203 \times RS - 0,373 \times SH \quad (6)$$

$$SH(\text{yigitlar}) = -50,1175 - 3,45151 \times RS + 1,2594 \times YUQS \quad (7)$$

$$T(\text{yigitlar}) = 87,6736 - 1,11034 \times RS - 0,5235 \times SH \quad (8)$$

3- sonli mashq. Joyida turib yugurish (Yugurish qadamlari miqdori/daq)

$$SH(\text{qizlar}) = 27,0845 - 2,65076 \times RS + 0,967219 \times YUQS \quad (9)$$

$$T(\text{qizlar}) = 128,433 - 1,10357 \times RS - 0,654431 \times SH \quad (10)$$

$$SH(\text{yigitlar}) = 30,9533 - 2,65076 \times RS + 0,985333 \times YUQS \quad (11)$$

$$T (\text{yigitlar}) = 135,402 - 1,11391 \times RS - 0,650371 \times SH (12)$$

Kadiorespirator tizimining funksional imkoniyatlarini oshirishga yordam beradigan minimal mashg'ulot yuklamasi YUQS 130-135 zarba/daqqa bo'lgandagi yuklama ekanligidan maksimal yuklama esa 135 zarba/ daq. ekanligidan kelib chiqsak, u xolda RS bahosi yomon bo'lgan talabalar uchun aerob jismoniy mashqlarni bajarish paytidagi jismoniy yuklamalar shiddati YUQS 130-140 zarba / daq.ga teng bo'lganda optimal xisoblanadi. (ehtiyotlovchi rejim); RS bahosi qoniqarsiz bo'lganda, YUQS –141 - 150 zarba/daq. RS qoniqarli bo'lganda YUQS – 151 – 160 zarba/ daq; RS yaxshi va a'lo bo'lganda, YUQS – 161 – 170 zarba/daq.

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